

SPIRITUAL AND MORAL ENVIRONMENT OF SOCIETY

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Annotation. In this article, the spiritual and moral environment of society differs from the social environment in that it appears as a factor directing the moods, views, aspirations of subjects of different classes of society to a certain goal, while, to this day, the social environment is studied as a micro, macro environment, however, in addition to the micro and macro environment, the presence, perhaps the structure of morality in inter-Environmental Communication has been noted to play a specific role.

Keywords: society, morality, epicenter, ethics, moral structure, moral consciousness.

The 21st century is characterized by the fact that to this day, the epicenter, which determines the total existence of mankind, has gone from economy, through politics, to spirituality. Because it is spirituality that has become a consensus that determines all the parameters of the existence of people. One of the indicators that determine the extremely relevance of the issue of solutions to the problem of the spiritual and moral environment in society is the global ethics of the present time and the analysis of national, spiritual and moral values, their development and improvement at the world crossroads is a new approach to the coverage of moral, spiritual relations in Uzbekistan.

Indeed, to date, the concept of the social environment has been widely studied in the scientific literature and its components have been studied: political, cultural, moral, literary, geographical, artificial environments. The social environment is studied as a space that reflects the relationship that humans see and inter – human and covers their social, economic, political, spiritual relationships in society in two

directions-as a micro and macro environment. While microenvironment refers to what is happening in and around a person, macroenvironment implies the existence of social, economic, political, ideological, spiritual realities of society as a whole. Hence, the social environment is a set of conditions and relationships that surround a person, social groups and influence and control his consciousness and behavior, activity. The spiritual and moral environment, on the other hand, as a component of the social environment of a particular society, uniquely reflects all complex social realities inherent in economic, social, political, spiritual environments in society. It is a space of existence in the unity of spiritual and moral values, moral norms, which are formed during the historical dissolution of a particular people, nation, Society, determine their worldview, purpose provision, lifestyle and traditions, ideals.

The spiritual and moral environment of society is distinguished from the social environment by the fact that it appears as a factor directing the moods, views, aspirations of the subjects of different classes of society to a certain goal. At the same time, to this day, when the social environment is studied, it is studied into a micro, macro environment, while in the spiritual and moral environment, in addition to the micro and macro environment, there is a connecting environment, a meso environment. Not only the size, territorial qualities of environments play a special role in this, but also the structure of morality in inter-Environmental Communication. Of course, the structure of morality forms an important part of the spiritual and moral environment of society, and it is first seen as the moral psychological and moral theoretical level of the moral structure of society. Secondly, the elements of the moral psychological and moral theoretical levels of the moral structure of society will exist in a state of inextricable connection with each other. In addition to these, moral consciousness, moral attitude, the cross-section of moral behavior are also important in the structure of morality. Because at the same time, moral behavior and moral attitudes themselves also have a complex structure. All the matter lies in the understanding and use of the states of harmony, existence of these structures in relation to spirituality. Currently, research on the problems of the

spiritual and moral environment assumes a new view of the social and moral environment, that is, from a spiritual and moral point of view.

Including, it is appropriate to connect these problems directly with the spiritual and moral environment of society in terms of interests, and it becomes clear that in the spiritual and moral environment of society, interests do not always serve a positive direction. Since it also has negative factors, the theoretical justification of problems directly in the spiritual and moral environment of society based on the principles of the general principle of communication and interaction of philosophy, the principle of progress, cause and effect, essence and phenomenon, abstraction to concretism is a requirement of the present day. In our opinion, the problems of the spiritual and moral environment of society include:

- associated with hegemony of a political nature, religious fanaticism, “invisible masks” in dreaming of a religious society, nationalism, chauvinism, radicalism, terrorism, separatism, ideological attacks;

- ideological risks of a social nature, infertility to national culture, negative consequences of moral vestirization, cosmopolitanism, social inactivity, lockdown, propaganda of cruel individualism, hedonism, legal illiteracy, humanism, slackening of the factors of purpose from the meaning of life and living, crime, mangrove;

- one-sided understanding of the economy with an economic character, talvasa under the guise of livelihood, conservatism, economic hypocrisy, in the brochure [1] “non-profit” entrepreneur, craftsman, farmer, producers on the occasion of “salvation” and “dirty bite” ;

- illusions, spiritual threats, spiritual aggressiveness, immorality, unbelief, loquacity, addiction, moral decay, blind imitation of Western life can be counted as “mass culture” as a result of the negative impact of globalization on a spiritual character.

In the formation of a healthy spiritual and moral environment in society, a philosophical approach to the issue of faith and faith of the individual occupies an important place. After all, faith and faith play the role of a supposedly unifying factor

in the Union of the inner world of the individual – “me” with an external whole universe. Consequently, his moral views and actions take direction in accordance with this worldview. A rare phenomenon that arises in the psyche (psychology) of the human mind and condition on the basis of a certain worldview – thanks to faith, a person acquires the will to live in strict compliance with the laws of society, discipline, norms of etiquette historically formed. Behaviors such as doing a useful deed every day, doing a noble deed, worldly interpretation of the norms of law in society, striving not to violate them are also from faith, believing in the right of both worldviews in the upbringing of a harmonious generation in our country, instilling in it the upbringing of individuals who have committed faith (devotional) [2]. Because the spiritual life of society should stand firmly on these two foundations, two supporting points. In a community environment, as long as any of these foundations are loose, the chances of falling into the DOM of the destructive forces listed above increase.

The experience of history and Life shows that it is possible to find a full-fledged answer to the difficult and complex questions of today, To Correctly Explain in every possible way the essence of the delicate relationship between secular and religious values, to clarify the meaning and purpose of the moral balance, to achieve the harmony of secular and religious values, to achieve[3].

The comprehensive study of the content, problems and conceptual solutions of the spiritual and moral environment of society, their effective use in national-spiritual development, has theoretical-practical significance. I.e.:

- to study the spiritual and moral environment of society on the scientific basis of moral laws and principles and solve its problems;
- raising the constructive side of the spiritual and moral environment of society, consistent social, moral analysis of spiritual and moral aspects based on the characteristics of modern national development;
- to strengthen the spiritual cooperation of people in the spiritual and moral environment, to form moral skills in the individual, to educate him spiritually and morally, to form and strengthen his will, to bring up truthful and humane;

-the development and regular improvement of a healthy spiritual and moral environment in society and its application to the continuous educational process, the deep absorption of national, socio-moral ideas corresponding to a truly spiritual and moral environment into the minds and hearts of our people, including young people;

- strengthening the mechanisms of succession to moral heritage, developing practical measures to achieve the idol of faith;

- It is noteworthy that the democratic society being built in Uzbekistan and the system of factors on which it is based are relatively new, rich in certain experiences and embody positive features. Therefore, the people of Uzbekistan, belonging to more than 130 nationalities and elats, live in harmony and harmony. This situation entails the development of indicators of the current existing spiritual and moral environment.

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